

Reflectance

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Bassac River, Southern Vietnam
by Monika Luabeya
Image credit: NASA

Quick Updates

- Josephina (Jojo) Matibag, a student who worked with Earth Lab scientists over the summer, recently wrote two blog posts about her work: "[Fast and Efficient Forest Inventory Using UAS Data](#)" and "[Bridging Art and Data Science at the Forest Carbon CodeFest.](#)" Read more about the latter below.
- Earth Lab celebrated its 10th birthday in fall 2025. We hosted a celebration event, which included remarks from Earth Lab members, a recycled poster-session, community-building events, and of course cake!

Grand Challenge
UNIVERSITY OF COLORADO BOULDER

NC RISCC Workshops

The North Central Regional Invasive Species & Climate Change ([NC RISCC](#)) network, founded by ESIL Deputy Director Chelsea Nagy, hosted two virtual stakeholder workshops in November 2025 and January 2026 to refine a draft Invasive Annual Grass adaptation menu. Adaptation menus compile climate-informed management actions and are used to guide planning under changing conditions. 39 members of the NC RISCC community, including researchers, land managers, extension specialists, and program coordinators, participated, providing direct feedback to improve the clarity, structure, and applicability of the menu. These workshops ensure that the menu reflects the needs of managers across the North Central region.

The broader RISCC Network, which includes six regional RISCCs, hosted the virtual International Invasive Species and Climate Change Conference (IISCCC) in December 2025. The event brought together over 700 researchers, managers, policy experts, and practitioners from across the globe to discuss emerging science, management challenges, and climate–invasive species interactions.

The North Central RISCC supported and contributed to a scenario-planning workshop hosted at the 2025 North American Invasive Species Management Association (NAISMA) annual conference. This session introduced participants to climate-informed scenario planning for invasive species management, with a focus on developing flexible strategies under uncertainty. Through exercises and facilitated discussion, attendees explored how climate change may alter invasive species trajectories and identified management actions across multiple future scenarios. Learn more [here](#).

Forest Carbon CodeFest Art Installation

In a recent collaboration with [NEST](#) (Nature, Environment, Science & Technology) Studio for the Arts, Earth Lab & ESIL team members have translated results from the 2024 Forest Carbon CodeFest into an artwork installation displayed in the Earth Lab/ESIL office space. During the CodeFest, teams used cyberinfrastructure and curated datasets to define scientific questions that advance our understanding of aboveground forest carbon dynamics as they relate to forest disturbance. Teams then collaboratively explored these questions and produced a fully open, reproducible code script. Several participants then transformed their results into art.

[Learn more](#)

The artists-in-attendance possess diverse backgrounds in various artistic mediums, from filmmaking to visual arts to musical composition, showcasing the diversity in creative expression. Each artist was encouraged to create a final piece for display in a public space, increasing exposure to the collaborative effort, and all pieces were produced as visual media. Read more about each piece on [our blog](#) and see their artwork in the Earth Lab/ESIL office space.

AFE & AGU

In December, 15 Earth Lab team members presented their work at two different scientific conferences. This year, both the Association for Fire Ecology (AFE) congress and the American Geophysical Union (AGU) annual meeting were hosted in New Orleans. Earth Lab attendees made many new connections and presented research and educational tools on topics such as fire ecology, ecological transformations, and open science infrastructure. Read more about some of their topics on our website [here](#). Additionally, Jennifer Balch, director of our sister organization, ESIL, received the prestigious honor of being named an [AGU Fellow](#).

AGU25

Data-Driven Solutions for Wildfire-Resilient Housing

Ongoing Research Highlight

In recent years, fires have grown larger, spread more quickly, and caused unprecedented damage to homes and communities. While climate, weather, and vegetation play important roles, the design, arrangement, and construction materials of buildings are also critical factors in determining how fires affect neighborhoods. Funded by the [ASCEND Engine](#), Dr. Virginia Iglesias (Earth Lab Director) and her team are leading a coordinated effort to better understand and strengthen the resilience of the built environment to wildfire. This project brings together fire incident records, satellite imagery, and building information to develop practical tools that assess how construction materials, defensible space, neighborhood design, and settlement patterns influence wildfire outcomes.

A central outcome of this work is the development of high-resolution maps that will show how likely individual buildings are to burn when exposed to wildfire, helping communities, planners, and emergency managers prioritize mitigation efforts, guide investments in safer construction, and strengthen preparedness and response strategies. In collaboration with the [Institute for Business and Home Safety](#) (IBHS), their team is also evaluating how different construction standards affect building expenses and identifying which design elements drive those costs.

Together, these efforts highlight a critical opportunity. Decisions about roofing, siding, spacing, and vegetation management made today will shape community safety for decades to come. By providing clear, credible, and practical information, their work supports smarter development and helps communities move from reacting to disasters toward building environments that are better prepared for them.

